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Background on FLUFET

Infectious zoonotic diseases that jump from animals to humans are on the rise, and the risk of a new pandemic is higher now than ever before. Future health models need to consider the close connection between human and animal health, and new technologies capable of continuously monitor places where the risk of pathogens transmission is higher (shared by animals and humans) are urgently needed to prevent the human, socio-political and economic cost from pandemics.

Continuous monitoring and harmonized data collection of animal farms are required by the European Parliament. However, current methods are not suitable for an in-situ, continuous and automatic detection, so today only a limited number of specific pathogens are monitored.

FLUFET will be the first automatized sensor able of continuously detecting a broad spectrum of viral targets, and with the unprecedented capability of detecting unknown viruses. This sensor will be based on graphene Field Effect Transistors (gFETs). FLUFET will detect infectious zoonotic threats before they spread to humans and create potential outbreaks, opening the door for a pandemic's prevention continuum. It will bring the possibility to incorporate the long-distance external factors heavily affecting human health at worldwide level.

FLUFET brings interesting opportunities for Health and pandemics experts and managers, Policymakers and regulatory/ standardization bodies, Animal farmers and their associations, Precision livestock farming solution providers, Investors and researchers in the multiple disciplines involved in the consortium.

FLUFET requires an interdisciplinary consortium including partners from computational biophysics, graphene technology, nanotechnology, sensing, microfluidics, virology, surface engineering and sensor design and electronics

Consortium Members

Nº	Role	Short Name	Legal Name	Country	PIC
1	COO	UDC	Universidade da Coruña	ES	999629718
2	BEN	BCMaterials	FUNDACION BCMATERIALS - BASQUE CENTRE FOR MATERIALS, APPLICATIONS AND NANOSTRUCTURES	ES	928273511
3	BEN (IO)	INL	Laboratorio Iberico Internacional de Nanotecnología	PT	988145985
4	BEN	BIOMA	ASOCIACION CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION COOPERATIVA EN BIOMATERIALES- CIC biomaGUNE	ES	998347572
5	BEN (IO)	ICGEB	INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR GENETIC ENGINEERING AND BIOTECHNOLOGY	IT	999470444
6	BEN	GSEMI	GRAPHENEA SEMICONDUCTOR SL	ES	910983940
7	BEN	VTT	TEKNOLOGIAN TUTKIMUSKESKUS VTT OY	FI	932760440

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Executive summary

In this document, which is the deliverable D2.3 of the FLUFET project, we report work progress and results from task 2.3 about the manufacture of dummy viruses and evaluation of their interaction with the engineered surface in work package 2 (“Engineering of the gFET surface”). This deliverable presents a comparative analysis of available virus-mimicking platforms and their suitability for the development of the FLUFET biosensor, and the synthesis strategies implemented for the selected systems. These results serve as a basis for further improvements to the sample delivery system and support the continued optimization of the platform’s sensing performance.

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Symbols, abbreviations and acronyms

ACE2	Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme 2
BSL	Biosafety Level
DLS	Dynamic Light Scattering
ELISA	Enzyme-Linked ImmunoSorbent Assay
EDC	1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide
EV	Extracellular Vesicle
gFET	Graphene Field Effect Transistor
LOD	Limit Of Detection
NE	NeutrAvidin
NHS	N-Hydroxysuccinimide Ester
NP	Nanoparticle
PS	Polystyrene
RBD	Receptor-Binding Domain
SE	Streptavidin
VLP	Virus-Like Particle
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The aim of Work Package 2 (WP2) is the engineering and optimization of the gFET surface for the FLUFET sensing platform. Within this framework, reliable model systems are required to evaluate receptor–surface interactions and to study the influence of shear forces under realistic microfluidic conditions. To address this need, fluorescent NPs were designed and manufactured as stable, safe model systems of the target viruses, enabling controlled and reproducible experimental studies during sensor development. Rapid detection of viral pathogens is essential for modern public health and global security, yet progress in biosensor development is constrained by the need to handle live, highly infectious viruses such as SARS-CoV-2, A/H1N1 and PUUV in high-containment Biosafety Level (BSL)-3/4 facilities. These requirements introduce substantial challenges for biosafety, biosecurity, and experimental variability that slow innovation.

Virus mimics have emerged as a transformative alternative, offering safe, non-infectious, and reproducible platforms that replicate the key structural and antigenic features of authentic viruses.^{1–3} These non-infectious NPs are engineered to replicate key structural and functional features of viruses, enabling detailed studies of virus-receptor interactions and sensor interface optimization without the risks associated with live pathogens, providing a critical bridge between fundamental research and the development of robust viral biosensors for laboratory and field applications.⁴

A wide range of virus mimics has been developed to reproduce key structural and functional characteristics of viral pathogens for research and technological applications.⁵ However, some systems still involve infectious particles or require complex biological production steps, introducing biosafety constraints and unnecessary experimental complexity. For the purpose of optimizing biosensor performance, three virus mimic platforms were identified as the most suitable approaches, as they provide a balanced combination of structural similarity to native viruses and safe, practical handling conditions:

- *Virus-like Particles (VLPs)*: These are self-assembling, non-replicating nanostructures composed of viral structural proteins (e.g., capsid proteins from HPV, hepatitis B, or influenza). They lack the viral genome, making them non-infectious while presenting authentic surface geometries and epitopes. Recent advances enable the functionalization of VLPs with specific ligands (e.g., SARS-CoV-2 spike proteins) for highly targeted interaction studies.^{6–8}
- *Pseudoviruses*: These are genetically engineered particles, typically using a core from a safe, enveloped virus (e.g., vesicular stomatitis virus, lentivirus) that is pseudo-typed with the surface glycoproteins of a target virus of interest (e.g., Ebola glycoprotein, SARS-CoV-2 spike).

They allow for the study of cell entry and neutralization in a BSL-2 setting but require cellular systems for production.^{9–11}

- *Synthetic NP Mimics*: These are non-viral constructs, such as liposomes, polymeric or metallic NPs, coated with recombinant viral proteins or synthetic receptor-binding domains (RBDs). Their size, surface charge, and ligand density can be precisely tuned, offering a platform to systematically dissect the factors governing binding affinity and kinetics, a key requirement for sensor optimisation.² Although sometimes it is necessary to mimic the complete virus structure in great detail, in many cases, taking only parts of the virus structures, such as the surface proteins, can be enough and is often a simpler approach.⁵ Moreover, due to their synthetic nature, additional properties, such as fluorescence, can be readily incorporated, enabling real-time monitoring of their behavior and dynamics through optical techniques.

A comparative analysis of the key characteristics of the three platforms based on the literature was conducted and summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of the comparative analysis of key characteristics of the three virus-mimicking platforms based on the literature (VLPs, Pseudoviruses and Synthetic Nanoparticle Mimics).

	Virus-Like Particles	Pseudoviruses	Synthetic Nanoparticle Mimics
Basic Structure	Self-assembled viral structural proteins forming capsid/envelope	Replication-deficient viral core with heterologous viral surface proteins	Inorganic or polymeric NP functionalized with viral proteins/peptides
Genetic Material	None	Present but replication-deficient	None
Surface Protein Presentation	Native-like, multivalent, correct spatial arrangement	Functional and biologically active	Controlled density; may lack native orientation unless engineered
Size and Morphology	Very close to authentic virus	Very close to authentic virus	Tunable size; shape often spherical but customizable
Reproducibility	Moderate (biological production variability)	Moderate	Very high
Stability	Moderate	Moderate–low	Very high
Biosafety Level Required	Low–moderate	Moderate (depending on system)	Very low
Production Complexity	High (cell expression systems)	High (cell-based viral production)	Low–moderate (colloidal synthesis + functionalization)
Compatibility with Fluorescent Labeling	Possible but biologically constrained	Possible	Excellent and easily tunable
Suitability for Microfluidics Studies	Moderate	Moderate	Excellent
Best Application Context	Biologically realistic interaction studies	Functional entry/binding studies	Biosensor optimisation, calibration, surface engineering studies

Therefore, *synthetic NP-based virus mimics*, from now on also called *dummy-viruses*, offer exceptional control over size, surface chemistry, and mechanical properties, along with high batch-to-batch reproducibility and long-term stability.^{4,5} They serve as safe and reproducible positive controls to test sensor sensitivity, specificity, and limit of detection (LOD) without high-containment facilities. These features make them particularly well-suited for biosensor development and testing, where systematic optimization of receptor density, orientation, and sensor-analyte interfaces is required. Moreover, their compatibility with fluorescent labelling and microfluidic platforms enables quantitative studies under controlled flow and shear conditions, positioning dummy-viruses as versatile and robust tools for accelerating biosensor optimization and translation toward real-world diagnostic applications.

The *synthetic NP-based virus mimics*, chosen in this WP simulate virus-like behavior, enabling a controlled assessment of the selectivity and affinity of the engineered gFET surfaces. Specifically, these dummy-viruses consist of a fluorescent NP functionalized with spike proteins, which allows realistic virus mimicking while facilitating the evaluation of the microfluidic sensing platform under controlled conditions, as established before.

2. Objectives

The objectives considered in this deliverable are the following:

- **To synthesize synthetic NP-based virus mimics**, through the controlled functionalization of NPs that replicate key structural, physicochemical, and surface characteristics of viral particles.
- **To evaluate and optimize its performance**, by systematically assessing the behavior of the virus mimics in relevant experimental conditions, identifying critical performance parameters, and refining the design to achieve optimal functionality and robustness.

3. Results

During T2.3, UDC focused on the synthesis of SARS-CoV-2 dummy-viruses by functionalizing fluorescent NPs, with diameters between 100 and 500 nm, with biotinylated Spike protein (SinoBiological, 40589-V27B) via a streptavidin (SE) or NeutrAvidin (NE)-biotin interaction.

For the development of these suitable dummy viruses for biosensor optimization, several key conditions must be fulfilled. The particles must reproduce the nanoscale dimensions and surface characteristics of real viruses while remaining fully non-infectious to ensure safe handling under standard laboratory conditions. They should allow controlled and reproducible surface functionalization, maintain structural stability under microfluidic flow, and be compatible with

fluorescence labelling to enable optical monitoring. At the same time, the system should avoid unnecessary biological complexity, ensuring robustness, reproducibility, and practical implementation during biosensor testing.

3.1 SYNTHESIS OF THE DUMMY VIRUSES

The initial synthesis strategy employed the well-established EDC-NHS chemistry to form amide bonds between SE or NE and the carboxylic acid groups present on the surface of FluoSpheres™ fluorescent microspheres (Invitrogen, MAN0001849), as is shown in the Figure 1, following the protocol described in the User Guide of the commercial NPs.¹²

Figure 1. Scheme of the synthetic strategy used in the initial approach for the preparation of the virus mimics. (A) Activation of surface carboxylic acid groups on commercial NPs via EDC/NHS coupling chemistry, enabling covalent amide bond formation with streptavidin. Adapted from: ThermoScientific. INSTRUCTIONS NHS and Sulfo-NHS. Technical Report 24500, Pierce Biotechnology, Rockford, IL, 2011. (B) Subsequent immobilization of the biotinylated viral surface protein through the specific and high-affinity biotin–streptavidin interaction.

However, this approach was discarded since the NPs exhibited significant aggregation in solution after the addition of the streptavidin, making them unsuitable for their use in the optimization of the biosensor (Figure 1A).

Consequently, commercially available NPs pre-functionalized with NE were selected to enable direct attachment of the biotinylated Spike protein (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Scheme of the synthetic strategy used for the preparation of the virus mimics employing NPs pre-functionalized with NE or SE on their surface.

The chosen polystyrene (PS) particles were FluoSphere NeutrAvidin-labelled (ThermoFisher, F-8774). Although the NE–biotin interaction is highly specific, initial characterization by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) and zeta potential measurements did not show clear evidence of successful functionalization. This may be attributed to intrinsic limitations of these techniques, as DLS measures the hydrodynamic diameter and is relatively insensitive to small changes in surface thickness, such as the addition of a protein layer of only a few nanometers, especially in polydisperse or slightly aggregated samples. Similarly, zeta potential measurements reflect overall surface charge and may not detect subtle modifications if the net surface charge remains largely unchanged after functionalization. Therefore, the absence of significant differences in these measurements does not necessarily indicate unsuccessful spike conjugation.

UDC, in collaboration with ICGB, is currently developing protocols to eliminate free spike proteins from the NP suspension to minimize nonspecific interactions, as well as establishing an ELISA-based functional assay to verify binding specificity. The outcomes of these optimization and validation experiments will be incorporated and updated in possible future versions of this deliverable.

Therefore, several different dummy-virus systems were synthesized to optimize the sensing platform, and all prepared NPs are summarized in Table 2. These included variants with controlled spike densities to better approximate the native viral surface. In particular, NPs functionalized with an average of 28 spike proteins per particle were prepared, reflecting reported estimates for the average spike density on SARS-CoV-2 virions, along with NPs bearing approximately three times this amount (84 spikes per NP) to evaluate the influence of surface protein density on binding behavior and sensor response.^{13,14}

Table 2. Overview of the synthesized dummy-virus and their main characteristics.

Material	NPs	Functionalization	Size (nm)	Fluorescence (abs/em) (nm)
PS	PS-SPIKE 200 nm	NE + 28B-Spike	200 + Spike	yellow-green (505/515)
	PS-SPIKE 200 nm	NE + 84B-Spike	200 + Spike	yellow-green (505/515)
SiO ₂	SiO ₂ -SPIKE 100 nm	SE + 84B-Spike	100 + Spike	yellow-green (488/510)
	SiO ₂ -SPIKE 100 nm	SE + 28B-Spike	100 + Spike	yellow-green (488/510)
	SiO ₂ -SPIKE 500 nm	SE + 28B-Spike	500 + Spike	red (535/646)

3.2 EVALUATION OF THEIR PERFORMANCE

Functionalized NPs, together with the additional materials outlined in Figure 3, were delivered to INL (T3.1) to systematically assess different binding interactions, namely, electrostatic interactions between carboxylic acids and amines (Figure 3A), avidin–biotin interaction (Figure 3B), and Spike–ACE2 recognition (Figure 3C), within WP3. This evaluation, shown in Deliverable 3.2 (Section 3.4 Particle delivery to the sensor), aimed to compare binding strengths and validate surface selectivity, affinity, and overall sensor performance under fluidic testing conditions.

Figure 3. Scheme of the three model systems used to systematically evaluate distinct binding interactions: (A) electrostatic interactions between carboxylic acid and amine groups; (B) specific avidin–biotin binding; and (C) biological recognition between Spike protein and ACE2 receptor.

However, chosen PS particles, synthesized using FluoSphere NeutrAvidin-labelled (ThermoFisher, F-8774), exhibited strong non-specific binding between the particles and the graphene, which was

proposed to be likely driven by π - π interactions between the PS core of the particles and the graphene surface (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Model systems for particle bindings to graphene. (A) Non-covalent functionalization of graphene with pyrene through π - π stacking. (B) Binding and detachment of a surface-attached particle induced by shear flow. (C) Hypothesis for strong non-specific binding of PS particles on graphene.

To address this issue, silica particles were evaluated as an alternative, given their more hydrophilic surface, which is dominated by silanol groups, compared to PS NPs, dominated by styrene moieties. This surface chemistry reduces nonspecific adsorption and limits direct interactions with graphene, particularly those arising from π - π stacking effects.

Initially, green, fluorescent SE silica particles (NanoCS, Si100-FCSV-1) were functionalized with the biotinylated Spike protein mentioned before. However, due to the failure of one of the lasers (488nm) in the confocal microscope used for the fluidic tests, which could not be repaired yet, we were not able to image these NPs.

Therefore, the NPs used for the next experiments were DiagNano™ Red Fluorescent, Streptavidin Silica Particles, 500 nm (CD Bioparticles, 0875-DNG-L270) from Gentaur. Moreover, studies of different PS NPs functionalizing glass surfaces were also performed and reported in Deliverable 3.2 (Section 3.4 Particle delivery to the sensor).

Moreover, different experiments with other NPs were performed for optimizing the system (Table 3).

Table 3. Overview of the NPs assessed under microfluidic conditions for the systematic study of binding interactions and optimization of the system performance.

Category	NPs	Functionalization	Size (nm)	Fluorescence (abs/em) (nm)
PS NPs	PS-NE 200 nm	NE	200	yellow-green (505/515)
	PS-SPIKE 200 nm	NE + 28B-Spike	200 + Spike	yellow-green (505/515)
	PS-SPIKE 200 nm	NE + 84B-Spike	200 + Spike	yellow-green (505/515)

	PS-COOH 100 nm	COOH	100	yellow-green (505/515)
	PS-COOH 100 nm	COOH	100	orange (540/560)
	PS-COOH 500 nm	COOH	500	red (580/605)
SiO₂ NPs	SiO ₂ -Av 100 nm	SE	100	yellow-green (488/510)
	SiO ₂ -Av 500 nm	SE	500	red (535/646)
	SiO ₂ -SPIKE 100 nm	SE + 84B-Spike	100 + Spike	yellow-green (488/510)
	SiO ₂ -SPIKE 100 nm	SE + 28B-Spike	100 + Spike	yellow-green (488/510)
	SiO ₂ -SPIKE 500 nm	SE + 28B-Spike	500 + Spike	red (535/646)
	Fluorescent Bare SiO ₂ (Powder)	—	120	—
Extracellular Vesicles (EVs)	EVs	—	~200 nm	Red (647/665)

The comparative evaluation of the different NP platforms, as shown in Deliverable 3.2 (Section 3.4 Particle delivery to the sensor), revealed distinct advantages and limitations associated with their material nature. SiO₂ NPs demonstrated minimal interaction with graphene surfaces; however, significant photobleaching and a tendency to form aggregates complicated fluorescence imaging and quantitative analysis under microfluidic conditions. EVs offered high biological relevance, but their simultaneous surface functionalization and stable fluorescent labelling proved technically challenging, limiting their practical applicability at this stage. In contrast, PS nanoparticles exhibited undesired interactions with graphene, yet provided strong and stable fluorescence signals that facilitated visualization and optimization studies. Consequently, preliminary interaction experiments were conducted using PS NPs on glass substrates, allowing systematic method development before graphene-based measurements for optimizing the performance of the biosensor.

4. Conclusions

The synthesis of multiple dummy virus systems based on different NP materials, including PS and silica, with controlled surface functionalization strategies was successfully achieved. The use of different fluorescent agents enabled optical tracking and facilitated interaction studies under microfluidic conditions, providing valuable tools for systematic biosensor optimization. The prepared platforms allowed the evaluation of material-dependent behaviors, surface interactions, and the influence of spike density, contributing to a better understanding of the parameters affecting sensor performance under safe conditions.

Further *in vitro* experiments are currently being conducted by ICGEB within the framework of Task 4.1. The characterization protocol under development is expected to provide additional validation of the functionalization efficiency and binding specificity achieved to date. In parallel, the synthesized NPs are being utilized in WP3, where INL is performing interaction studies under microfluidic conditions to assess binding behavior and sensing performance in dynamic environments. If the outcomes of these activities identify additional requirements concerning NP properties, these will be incorporated into subsequent updates of the deliverable as the optimization process progresses.

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